

A modified, fast, and conservative technique for direct post and core pattern fabrication.

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Abstract

This article describes a fast and time-saving procedure for fabricating direct post and core pattern. The technique employs a one-component light polymerizing resin material and a drill-matched burnout plastic post as an alternative to auto-cured acrylic resins.

This technique can produce dimensionally accurate castings, sparing valuable time and effort during fabrication. It also preserves valuable tooth structure and does not expose oral tissues to polymerization heat or chemical insults from excess monomer as in conventional techniques.

INTRODUCTION

For a long time, custom cast post and cores have been accepted as a treatment modality for endodontically treated teeth. DuraLay® (Reliance Dental Manufacturing LLC, USA), an autopolymerized acrylic resin, has been introduced for this purpose and accepted as a material for direct and indirect pattern fabrication¹; unfortunately, one of its drawbacks is dimensional changes caused by polymerization shrinkage or storage protocol^{2,3}. This might lead to inaccuracies⁴ affecting retention and resistance of final castings.⁵ Moreover, in the conventional method, round-end tapered diamond burs used for post-space preparation⁶ have the potential to cause significant loss of tooth structure⁷, violating the 1 mm suggested minimum for residual wall thickness⁸, which may result in non-restorable fractures.⁹ That is not the case with the more conservative post-space preparation using Gates Glidden and parallel-sided drills (GGDs) used for fiber post preparation^{7,10}.

This article addresses a fast and conservative technique for fabricating direct post and core pattern through using drill-matched (as with fiber posts) burnout

plastic posts (BPP) and one component thixotropic* light polymerizing resin material (LPRM).

TECHNIQUE

1- Select the length and width of BPP (Itena® clinical products) by aid of a peri-apical radiograph so that it occupies the two thirds of canal length, leaving a minimum of 1 mm root wall thickness laterally (Fig. 1A).

2- Heat a fine-tip plugger attached to heat source (System B cordless, Kerr) up to 200°C and insert it into canal, to a depth of two thirds of canal length. Allow the tip to cool for 15 seconds, then apply a single burst of heat for 1 second and then remove the tip.

3- Widen post-hole laterally using low-speed Peeso-reamers (Dentsply Maillefer) in a sequential manner up to one size smaller than the post-matched reamer. Finalize post-hole shaping by using a low-speed post-matched reamer.

4- Mark the predetermined length on the burnout plastic post (BPP) and insert it into canal to ensure proper seating.

5- Remove BPP out of canal and eliminate any undercut coronally using a round-end tapered bur #H856U.314.016 (Komet Dental, Brasseler) so that remaining coronal tissues are either parallel or perpendicular to the post.

6- Start fabricating the core by applying light vibration motion while injecting a ring of LPRM

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Fig. 1. A: Burnout plastic posts (BPP). B: One component thixotropic light polymerizing resin material (LPRM).

Fig. 2a: Injecting a ring of LPRM around BPP.

Fig. 2b. LPRM ring around BPP.

Fig. 2c. Core completed using paint-and-cure protocol.

Fig. 2d. Light polymerizing completed core.

Fig. 2e. Finished core ready for casting.

(Primopattern LC Gel) (Fig. 1B) from syringe around the post while securing it under finger pressure (Fig. 2a).

7- Stop the vibrational motion for the material to turn into gel and hold together, and light cure using Elipar™ S10 curing light (3M, ESPE) for 10 seconds (Fig. 2b).

8- Use paint-and-cure protocol, complete the core of the pattern (Figs. 2c, 2d).

9- Hold the remaining part of the post and pull the pattern out of the canal and test for fit.

10- Use yellow coded round-end tapered bur #856EF.314.016 (Komet, Brasseler) to cut the excessive part of post and to refine axial and occlusal parts of pattern-core (Figs. 2e, 2f).

11- Send to dental laboratory for casting (Fig. 2g).

DISCUSSION

This article describes a simple and fast procedure in which drills, that match the configuration of the burnout plastic post, are utilized for a more conservative post-space preparation; this eliminates undercuts or over-

Fig. 2f. A; Finished direct post and core pattern. B; Casted post and core.

Fig. 2g. Cemented post and core.

widening during post-space preparation when using conventional tooth-preparation diamond burs.

This technique does not require further radicular adjustment of the post to the canal and canal lubrication, which adds to the procedure time during application and removal. It also spares the operator from working against the clock during repeated loosening and reseating post against setting time of DuraLay®. In addition, it provides control of the thickness and shape of radicular part of the post which may be crucial to post or tooth longevity¹¹.

The core material is fabricated using one-component light polymerizing resin material (LPRM) composed of a mixture of light cured aliphatic methacrylate and acrylate resins, initiators, and fillers (Primopattern LC Gel); this material is thixotropic* upon slight vibration of the application tip; its viscosity decreases and becomes more fluid for better wettability to record all details and then returns to its gel state to preserve its shape before curing; that is unlike DuraLay® which flows and slumps when it is applied by bead-brush technique and has lower dimensional stability than LPRM upon setting¹².

Acrylic resin materials undergo volumetric contraction (shrinkage) during polymerization process. One study² reported that 80% of all the shrinkage of DuraLay® resin occurs before 17 minutes and 95% before 3 hours, at room temperature². Further shrinkage might occur during storage between fabrication and casting, especially that there is no clear proposed protocol regarding storage conditions of DuraLay®. Studies in this regard provided conflicting results¹³⁻¹⁶.

The proposed technique is simple, conservative, and predictable, but it is not effective in oval-shaped canals and it needs antirotational features in rootface.

CONCLUSION

The present technique is a simple, fast, time-efficient, predictable, and reliable alternative to the conventional DuraLay® autopolymerized acrylic pattern resin in fabricating cast post and core. Further studies are warranted to verify our claims.

* *Thixotropy is a time-dependent shear thinning property. Certain fluids or gels that are thick or viscous under static conditions will flow over time when shaken, agitated, sheared, or otherwise stressed. They then take a fixed time to return to a more viscous state.*

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